

Assessing Loaded Reverberation Chambers: Calculating Threshold Metrics

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Abstract

In this paper we present two versions of a threshold metric of a loaded reverberation chamber. One metric is based on the chamber quality factor (Q), and the other is based on the volume of the loaded reverberation chamber. These metrics are baseline quantities that must be exceeded in order to have an effective reverberation chamber. We present an application of these metrics for the case of a reverberation chamber loaded with spheres composed of lossy materials.

INTRODUCTION

Reverberation chambers are being used for a wide range of measurement applications. In a large number of these measurements, the chamber is inherently loaded with various objects, some of which exhibit losses. A key issue is how a measurement loads a chamber and affects performance. A reverberation chamber exhibits optimal performance (field uniformity, etc.) within a certain range of power loss or cavity Q . The case of ideal lossless (or infinite Q) results in poor reverberation performance. A chamber of infinite Q results in a line spectrum in the measured field, causing the chamber not to work continuously across the entire spectrum. Wall losses due to finite conductivity avoid this ideal case, which can also be improved by the addition of some lossy material (possibly by reducing wall conductivity). However, the addition of more lossy material will again degrade the performance. In practice, a typical chamber has lossy walls and is usually loaded with other objects. Our concern, then, is how much loss can be tolerated before the chamber's effectiveness degrades and becomes unacceptable.

There are very few studies in the literature that have investigated the degradation of the chamber performance with increased loading. Results of one such experiment [1] are shown in Figure 1. This

figure shows the standard deviation over random locations of the average total squared electric field. The standard deviation is then plotted as a function of the number of lossy objects placed in the chamber, in this case 500 ml bottles filled with water. It is seen that as the number of lossy objects increases, the standard deviation of the average field between the selected measurement points increases, indicating reduced point-to-point field uniformity and degraded performance.

Besides using the field statistics as a means of assessing chamber performance, it is also possible to investigate the degradation of the chamber Q and the degradation of the useable volume of a reverberation chamber. Furthermore, it is possible to develop an expression for these threshold metrics that must be exceeded in order to achieve an effective reverberation chamber. In this paper we present an expression for a threshold chamber Q and a useable volume of a loaded reverberation chamber, which will allow quick evaluation of a chamber.

Figure 1: The effect of loading on the standard deviation of the average squared total electric field.

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CALCULATION OF THRESHOLD METRICS

To derive these threshold metrics, we first represent the power density S_d from direct transmission of power P_t by an isotropic antenna in free space:

$$S_d = \frac{P_t}{4\pi r^2}, \quad (1)$$

where r is the distance from the antenna. From [2], the scalar mean power density in a reverberation chamber is given by

$$\langle S_r \rangle = \frac{\lambda Q P_t}{2\pi V}, \quad (2)$$

where V is the chamber volume and λ is the free-space wavelength.

At some effective radius r_e , these two power densities become equal. This effective radius is given by

$$r_e = \sqrt{\frac{V}{2\lambda Q}}. \quad (3)$$

For a radius less than r_e , the power density in the chamber is dominated by S_d (i.e., direct coupling), and for a radius greater than r_e the reverberation power density dominates.

This radius r_e corresponds to a spherical volume of

$$V_{re} = \frac{4}{3}\pi r_e^3 = \frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{V}{2\lambda Q}\right)^{3/2}. \quad (4)$$

For an effective or efficient reverberation chamber, this volume (V_{re}) must be much less than the actual chamber volume:

$$V_{re} \ll V. \quad (5)$$

V_{re} can be used as a metric for assessing the chamber performance, i.e., if the actual volume of the chamber is much larger than V_{re} , the chamber can be considered an effective reverberation chamber.

A threshold of the chamber Q can be obtained by returning to expression (4), and realizing that expression (5) also implies

$$Q \gg Q_{thr}, \quad (6)$$

where

$$Q_{thr} = \left(\frac{4\pi}{3}\right)^{2/3} \frac{V^{1/3}}{2\lambda}. \quad (7)$$

This is the value that the Q of the chamber must exceed for the reverberation chamber to be effective.

CHAMBER WITH LOSSY SPHERES

To illustrate how loading a chamber affects these two threshold metrics, a chamber with lossy spheres was investigated. In order to calculate the r_e and V_{re} , the Q of a chamber with lossy spheres is needed, while Q_{thr} is a function only of V and λ . The Q associated with a chamber with finitely conducting walls and with N lossy spheres is given by the following [2]:

$$\frac{1}{Q} = \frac{1}{Q_{wall}} + \frac{1}{Q_{sphere}}, \quad (7)$$

where Q_{wall} is associated with the wall loss and Q_{sphere} is associated with loss due to the N spheres in the chamber. The smaller of Q_{wall} and Q_{sphere} will be the dominant contributor to Q . Q_{wall} is expressed as

$$Q_{wall} = \frac{3V}{2S\delta\mu_r}, \quad (8)$$

where S is the surface area of the walls of the chamber, μ_r is the relative permeability of the walls, δ is the skin depth of the wall, given by

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\omega\mu_0\mu_r\sigma_w}}, \quad (9)$$

and σ_w is the wall conductivity. Q_{sphere} is expressed as

$$Q_{sphere} = \frac{2\pi V}{\lambda \langle \sigma_a \rangle}, \quad (10)$$

where $\langle \sigma_a \rangle$ is the averaged absorption cross section ($\langle \rangle$ indicates an incidence angle averaged over 4π steradians and over all polarizations). The absorption cross section can be that of a single object or a summation for N objects, i.e.,

$$\langle \sigma_a \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N \langle \sigma_{oi} \rangle. \quad (11)$$

If the objects are identical, this reduces to

$$\langle \sigma_a \rangle = N \langle \sigma_o \rangle, \quad (12)$$

where $\langle \sigma_o \rangle$ is the absorption cross section of a single object or sphere. For a homogeneous sphere the absorption cross section can be expressed in closed form in terms of the Riccati-Bessel function, and has the following form (for details see [3])

$$\langle \sigma_o \rangle = \pi a^2 (\eta_t - \eta_s), \quad (13)$$

where η_t and η_s are efficiency factors given by

$$\eta_t = \frac{2}{(ka)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (2n+1) \operatorname{Re}[a_n + b_n] \quad (14)$$

and

$$\eta_s = \frac{2}{(ka)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (2n+1) [|a_n|^2 + |b_n|^2]. \quad (15)$$

The parameters a_n and b_n are functions of the Riccati-Bessel function and are given in [3]. Actually, the absorption cross section for a homogeneous sphere is independent of both the incidence angle and polarization of the incident field and no averaging is required.

The absorption cross section for a lossy sphere with two different radii (denoted by a) composed of salt water (i.e., $\epsilon_r = 80 - j36.9$) is calculated using the above approach. Values for $\langle \sigma_o \rangle$ as a function of frequency are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: $\langle \sigma_o \rangle$ for two spheres with $\epsilon_r = 80 - j36.9$.

This absorption cross-section can then be used to determine the Q of a chamber with various numbers of lossy spheres. Figure 3 shows the Q of a chamber for various numbers of spheres ($a = 14$ cm) as a function of frequency. These results are for the NIST reverberation chamber, which is $2.8 \times 3.1 \times 4.6$ m and has $\sigma_w = 8.8 \times 10^6$ S/m. For this radius of spheres and the conductivity of the NIST chamber, Q is dominated by Q_{sphere} . As expected, the Q of the chamber decreases with increasing number of lossy spheres. Also shown in the figure is the threshold Q_{thr} value. It is seen that for 300 spheres, the Q is only about an order of magnitude above the threshold. Measurements were made in the NIST reverberation chamber (with dimensions the same as in the above example) with 255 bottles filled with lossy fluids. These measurements indicated that around 255 bottles was the limit for good performance ($\text{std}|E|^2 < 3$ dB), which is consistent with the results shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Q for a chamber loaded with lossy spheres, where N is the number of spheres.

The alternative way of evaluating the degradation in the reverberation chamber performance is to investigate the change of the volume V_{re} as presented in Eq. (4) and in the inequality in Eq. (6). Using the Q calculated for the chamber with lossy spheres (given

in Figure 3), r_e and V_{re} are calculated and results are shown in Figures 4 and 5. In Figure 4, we see that as the number of lossy spheres in the chamber increases, r_e approaches the chamber limited r (i.e., one-half the smallest chamber dimension). In Figure 5, we see that V_{re} approaches the actual volume of the chamber. As r_e and V_{re} become larger, then the reverberation chamber becomes less effective.

Figure 4: r_e for a chamber loaded with lossy spheres, where N is the number of spheres.

Figure 5: V_{re} for a chamber loaded with lossy spheres, where N is the number of spheres.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper we presented two types of metrics to assess the loading of a reverberation chamber. We applied these metrics to a reverberation chamber loaded with an increasing number of lossy spheres.

The threshold metric of Q (Q_{thr}) gives a value that the Q of the chamber must exceed for an effective or efficient reverberation chamber. The inequality in Eq. (6) says Q must be large compared to Q_{thr} . The question that needs to be investigated in the future is: how much must the actual Q exceed Q_{thr} to have an effective reverberation chamber? The same can be said about V_{re} and r_e , i.e., how much smaller does r_e or V_{re} need to be when compared to the chamber limiting values, to have an effective reverberation chamber.

Obviously as these metrics approach their threshold values, the chamber effectiveness decreases. For example, the standard deviation of the average field increases as chamber loading increases, see Figure 1. The real question is: how do these metrics relate to the standard deviation of the field inside a reverberation chamber? These topics are part of our ongoing work.

REFERENCE

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